

IMPLICATIONS OF POPULATION GROWTH AND MIGRATION ON URBANIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The study aims to find out the relationship and impact of the percentage of people living in urban areas on the Standard of Living and Labour Force Participation Rate.

Design Methodology: The Standard of Living component is measured using the GNI Per Capita (2011 US\$PPP). Using data from the World Bank Database, correlation and regression analysis is done among Urban Population % as well as on GNI Per Capita and Labour Force Participation Rate separately.

Findings: The percentage of Urban Population is very strongly related and has a significant impact on both GNI Per Capita and Labour Force Participation Rate. It can be used to explain the trends in both the variables.

Research Implications: The study confirms previous research that rise in urban population leads to increase in the standard of living. However, GNI Per Capita, even if it is used by the United Nations for its Human Development Index's standard of living indicator, hides the true story of inequalities existing in the country. A country might show a high per-capita income and still have about one-fourth of its population living in abject poverty.

Scope for future work / Research limitations: Further studies can be done on how to increase employment opportunities in the rural areas, as well as how to reduce urbanization because of the current problems in urban areas. It should be looked into how the standard of living in rural areas can be improved. By standard of living, income should not be the only thing taken into account, but rather, their overall quality of life.

Originality/value: Increase in urban population over the years has its benefits in the form of increased income and standard of living but it also comes with the downsides of population explosion, crime rates, and a host of environmental problems. Even so, we need to find out if urban population drives the people's standard of living as well as how much of the working-age population goes into the labour force.

Key words: open ended tax saving mutual fund, mediator, ANOVA, partial mediation

Paper type: Research paper

INTRODUCTION

More over half of the world's population, or roughly 55 percent, lives in cities, a figure that the United Nations predicts would rise to 68 percent by 2050. People gravitate to cities because they offer more options. Higher jobs, better wages, better living conditions,

education, and healthcare are all examples of this. In terms of numbers, the urban population of the world has grown from 751 million in 1950 to 4.5 billion in 2019.

Despite having a lower level of urbanisation than other continents, Asia is home to 54% of the world's urban population. India and China are the largest contributors to this statistic. Furthermore, India and China are predicted to be the primary drivers of the estimated 68 percent growth rate by 2050.

Due to population increase and migration, India experienced rapid urbanisation. In quest of better prospects, people from rural areas went to towns and cities. The largest migratory hotspots were Delhi, Mumbai, Bengaluru, and Chennai. Later, as the economy grew, more people moved to cities, accelerating the migration of people.

This enormous exodus affected people's occupational preferences as well as how each sector contributes to India's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The tertiary or service sector, which contributed roughly 54.3 percent of GDP in 2018-19, has surpassed the primary sector as the leading contributor.

Another element that has contributed to urbanisation is government initiatives in the past (and now) that have made relocating to cities more appealing. Special Economic Zones, infrastructural improvements, and the liberalisation of restrictions for starting a factory or a business boosted prospects, drawing an increasing number of individuals.

Incomes have risen as the urban population has grown. Urban areas are the epicentre of the manufacturing and service sectors, both of which generate substantial wealth. Bengaluru, for example, drew a large number of individuals due to its thriving IT sector. It became renowned as India's Silicon Valley. Because of the increasing demand for IT workers, towards the conclusion of their careers, young IT professionals began earning the same amount of money as their parents.

The issue of overcrowding, on the other side, arose. The expansion of economic and job prospects could not keep up with the tremendous influx of people into cities. As a result, people were unable to obtain work or adequate accommodation, putting them in a difficult situation.

The cities of Delhi and Mumbai are outstanding instances of this. Cities have become overcrowded as a result of overpopulation. Slums are a concern in Mumbai. Dharavi, a Mumbai slum, is Asia's largest slum, with thousands of inhabitants crammed into a small space. Delhi is concerned about the emergence of unauthorised colonies.

Other issues include severe water shortages in Chennai and Delhi, increased crime rates, particularly in Delhi, poverty, rising income inequality, labour exploitation, and a slew of other issues. It also contributed to the issue of educated unemployment or underemployment, in which graduates are either engaged in jobs that are unrelated to their qualifications or are unable to find work at all.

In 2019, India's labour force participation rate was 49.3%, according to the World Bank. The Labour Force Participation Rate is calculated by dividing the number of active

workers and those actively seeking work by the total population of working-age persons, or those aged 16 to 64.

This indicates that in 2019, just over half of the working-age population was unemployed. We must understand that this result indicates that nearly 51% of the working-age population did not look for work. This is a major source of concern for India, as it demonstrates that the country's enormous population and potential skill pool are either underutilised or not employed at all.

Higher urban population provides benefits in terms of increased wealth and style of living, but it also has drawbacks such as population explosion, increased crime rates, and a slew of environmental issues. Nonetheless, we must determine whether urban population influences people's living standards and how much of the working-age population enters the labour force.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In their work, *Urbanization, Urban Poverty, and Health of the Urban Poor: Status, Challenges, and the Way Forward* (2007), Siddharth Agarwal and Aravinda Satyavada discovered that the poor make up a significant section of our cities and towns. About a quarter of India's population, or 25.7 percent, lives in cities. As a result, poverty is no longer a rural issue. In metropolitan regions, there are significant differences between the urban poor and the better-off portions. Indeed, slum inhabitants in cities have health problems that are sometimes worse than those who live in rural areas.

R. B. Bhagat reported in his essay *Emerging Pattern of Urbanization in India* (2011) that, according to the 2011 Census, urbanisation has increased faster than projected, reversing the downward trend in the urban population growth rate seen in the 1980s and 1990s. Furthermore, for the first time since independence, the absolute increase in the urban population outpaced the increase in the rural population. This could cause challenges in terms of infrastructure and other municipal amenities in metropolitan regions.

In his study, *Quality of Living in India in the Post-Liberalization Era* (2017), Radhagobinda Basak discovered that the percentage of Indians living below the intended standard of living is falling, both in rural and urban areas. In the two decades following 1991, this figure fell by 18.25 percent in metropolitan areas, or around 0.96 percent each year on average. After India became a globalised economy, this downward tendency began.

Slum dwellers in highly urbanised cities had better access to healthcare, basic amenities, and infrastructure than slum dwellers in less urbanised regions, according to Mala Mukherjee's paper, *Mapping of Regional Disparity in Standard of Living: Issues and Challenges to Urban Resilience in India* (2017).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The goal of this study is to look into the relationship between the percentage of individuals who live in cities and their level of living as well as their labour force participation rate. The researchers also want to examine if the urban population has an effect on these characteristics.

This is a quantitative research project. For the purposes of this investigation, secondary data was utilised. Urban Population (percentage of total population), Gross National Income Per Capita (2011 US\$PPP), and Labor Force Participation Rate are the variables used. GNI Per Capita and Labour Force Participation Rate are dependent variables, while Urban Population Percentage is an independent variable.

These factors were chosen to see if more urbanisation improves people's overall standard of life, as assessed by GNI per capita in 2011 Purchasing Power Parity. It should also be investigated whether urbanisation has an effect on labour force participation rates.

From 1991 to 2019, the data for these variables was gathered from the World Bank Database. Because the study's goal is to look into India, only data from that country was acquired.

Correlation and regression analysis were employed in the study for analysis. The association between Urban Population and each of the dependent variables might be discovered using correlation analysis. Regression analysis could be used to take things a step further and determine if fluctuations in the dependent variables can be explained by Urban Population. A Simple Linear Regression model is used in the regression analysis.

For analysis, the statistical software SPSS is employed. To assess the significance of the coefficients and the correctness of the regression models, t-Test and ANOVA tests are used in addition to correlation and regression analyses.

H1: There is indeed a meaningful correlation and influence of urban population and standard of living

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: Correlation between Urban Population % and GNI Per Capita, Labour Force Participation Rate

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation	p-value
Urban Population %	GNI Per Capita	0.986	0.000
Urban Population %	Labour Force Participation Rate	-0.942	0.000

It's also worth noting that both relationships are statistically significant when looking at the p-values. The correlation coefficient is significant if the p-value is less than 0.05. We can state with 99 percent confidence that there is a clear, significant link between Urban Population percent and both dependent variables because the p-values are less than 0.01. Because the relationships are considerable, it's a good idea to dig deeper.

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URBAN POPULATION % AND LABOUR FORCE PARTICIPATION RATE

Table 3: Regression coefficients between Urban Population % and Labour Force Participation Rate

Variables	Coefficients	t-statistic	p-value	R-squared	F-statistic	p-value
Constant	90.362	41.172	.000	0.913	253.218	0.000
Urban Population %	-1.172	-15.752	.000			

According to the model, when the urban population grows by a percentage point, the labour force participation rate falls by 1.172 percent on average.

The t-test is used to determine whether the regression coefficients are significant. For Urban Population Percent, the t-test and related p-value are -15.752 and 0.000, respectively. We can say with 99 percent confidence that urban population percent is a significant predictor of the Labour Force Participation Rate because the p-value is less than 0.01.

The R-squared value of 0.913 indicates that the Urban Population percent explains 90.362 percent of the variation in the Labour Force Participation Rate, indicating that the model is accurate. This indicates that the model described above is quite accurate.

The ANOVA test is used to determine the model's validity. The F-Statistic value is 253.218, whereas the p-value is less than 0.01. As a result, we can conclude that the above model is accurate in predicting the Labor Force Participation Rate with a 95% confidence level.

FINDINGS

The standard of living has a statistically significant association with the urban population. The standard of living tends to rise in tandem with the percentage of people living in cities. This association, however, does not suggest causation.

The GNI Per Capita may be estimated using a simple linear regression model, which indicates that the Urban Population Percentage is a significant predictor of the GNI Per Capita. It means that an increase or decrease in urban population has a major impact on GNI per capita behaviour.

Job prospects in urban locations are more lucrative than those in rural areas. People migrate to cities in pursuit of greater chances and higher earnings, as previously stated. Higher income leads to increased consumption, which raises the standard of living. As the urban population grows, so does the per-capita income.

The Labor Force Participation Rate and the Urban Population Percentage tend to move in opposite directions. The number of persons who are currently employed or seeking employment as a percentage of the total working-age population tends to drop as the amount of people living in metropolitan regions grows.

Because this is a correlation analysis, it does not imply that the fall in the Labour Force Participation Rate is caused by the urban population percentage. The two factors, however, have a strong and significant relationship.

The simple linear regression model used to estimate the Labour Force Participation Rate using Urban Population Percentage shows that one of the major explanations of the decline in India's Labour Force Participation Rate over time is the increase in Urban Population Percentage. In comparison to the working-age population, the number of persons employed or seeking employment falls as more people relocate to metropolitan regions.

In comparison to rural areas, urban areas provide easier access to education and a higher quality of education. It leads to better jobs and higher wages. Higher salaries would suggest that parents can afford to send their children to college.

As a result, as the urban population grows, so does literacy, the average number of years spent in school, and the number of persons enrolled in universities or other higher education institutions.

Aside from that, India's working-age population includes those aged 16 to 64. The number of people pursuing post-secondary education (at least till the age of 22) is increasing, indicating that they are not actively seeking employment. Retirees in the age group of 61 to 64 are not looking for work because the majority of people retire at the age of 60.

These might be viewed as contributing factors to the decline in the labour force participation rate as the urban population grows. This reason for the drop has little impact on the economy because an increasing number of people are using their time when they reach 16 to further their education and enhance their abilities. As a result, it would be good for the economy in the long run.

We should also keep in mind that this isn't the main cause of the downturn. Underemployment is a problem in India as well. Another factor contributing to the drop is people's unwillingness to work in professions that are unrelated to their degrees and talents. In recent years, there has been a scarcity of job possibilities in India. As a result, when there are no prospects to use their skills, youths do not actively seek employment.

DISCUSSION

The study backs up earlier research that shows that as the urban population grows, so does the standard of living. However, even though GNI Per Capita is utilised by the United Nations as a standard of living indicator in the Human Development Index, it masks the underlying tale of inequality in the country. Even if a country has a high per-capita income, around a quarter of its people lives in abject poverty.

It does not imply that individuals should relocate to cities in order to improve their living conditions. While this is correct in one respect, it will have unintended consequences such as overcrowding, unemployment, a housing problem, increased living costs, and so on. These negative consequences may partially balance the good ones. More research on income inequality and how to eliminate them can be done in this way.

More research may be done on how to boost employment possibilities in rural areas and how to prevent urbanisation as a result of present urban challenges. It should be investigated how to raise the level of living in rural communities. Income should not be the sole factor considered when determining a person's level of living, but rather their total quality of life.

When it comes to the Labor Force Participation Rate, the percentage of the population living in cities is a significant element in influencing this figure. While this is positive since it indicates that more people are opting to pursue higher education, the focus should be on how to create appropriate opportunities so that the right skill is employed for the right job. The youth should be able to see a return on their educational efforts.

Other explanations for the decline in the labour force participation rate can be investigated through research. Surveys can be undertaken to determine why certain people do not want to work and how to help them find work, as well as suggested remedies. Such research will undoubtedly benefit India, which has a big skill pool.

CONCLUSION

The goal of this study was to show that the urban population has an impact on overall living standards and the labour force participation rate. Not only that, but the percentage of the population living in cities can be used to forecast both factors. When it comes to decreasing inequities and improving the labour force participation rate, India has a long way to go. As the percentage of people living in cities grows, so does the standard of living. The Labour Force Participation Rate, on the other hand, drops as the urban population grows. People are increasingly moving to cities to work in the manufacturing and service industries, consequently raising their income. Education becomes more accessible when one's money rises, and the literacy rate rises. The Labor Force Participation Rate has fallen over time, and it is strongly correlated with urban population in a negative direction, with urban population having a considerable influence. More research can be done to determine why it is dwindling and how to boost it.

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